

THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS & MANAGEMENT

A Study on Adaptation of Electric Vehicles in India: Challenges and Opportunities

Dr. P.Govindan

Assistant Professor in Commerce, Department of Commerce, K.S.Rangasamy College of Arts
and Science (Autonomous), Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract:

India is undergoing a significant transition towards electric mobility to address environmental challenges, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and promote sustainable development. This study examines the incorporation of electric vehicles (EVs) in India, focusing on key obstacles and emerging opportunities. By leveraging secondary data from government reports, industry publications, and academic literature, the study assesses trends in EV adoption, infrastructure improvements, and policy support. The findings reveal that EV adoption in India has surged from approximately 50,000 units in 2016 to over 2.08 million units in 2024, largely driven by electric two- and three-wheelers. However, adoption in sectors such as passenger cars, buses, and trucks remains limited due to high upfront costs, inadequate charging infrastructure, financing challenges, and low consumer awareness. The study also highlights opportunities, including strong government initiatives, increasing investments, technological advancements, and favourable consumer attitudes. Policy measures such as the FAME schemes and the PM E-DRIVE initiative have played a crucial role in promoting EV adoption. The study concludes that while India has made significant progress, achieving the 30% EV penetration target by 2030 will require coordinated efforts in infrastructure development, policy reforms, financing solutions, and public awareness.

Keywords: Electric vehicles, India, challenges, technology, opportunities, infrastructure

1. Introduction

The global shift towards sustainable transportation has accelerated the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs), driven by concerns about climate change, environmental degradation, and energy security. India, acknowledged as one of the fastest-growing economies and the third-largest automobile market, is facing increasing challenges related to air pollution and its reliance on imported fossil fuels. In response, the Indian government has made a strategic commitment to transition towards electric mobility as part of its broader sustainability goals. India aims to achieve a 30% EV penetration in total vehicle sales by 2030. This ambitious target is supported by initiatives such as the National Electric Mobility Plan, the FAME I and II schemes, and the PM E-DRIVE program. The uptake of EVs in India has shown steady growth, with sales increasing significantly over the past decade. However, the overall penetration rate remains relatively low compared to global leaders like China, the United States, and the European Union.

Despite policy support and technological advancements, several challenges hinder widespread adoption. These challenges include high initial costs, inadequate charging infrastructure, financing constraints, and consumer misconceptions regarding the performance and reliability of EVs. Additionally, fragmented policies across states and the lack of standardized systems complicate adoption. The existing body of literature highlights the environmental benefits and economic potential of electric vehicles (EVs), while also recognizing the challenges to their widespread adoption in developing countries such as India. Nevertheless, a research gap persists regarding the interactions among infrastructural, financial, technological, and behavioural factors that affect EV adoption. This study aims to explore the challenges and opportunities associated with the adoption of EVs in India. The objectives include analyzing current adoption trends, identifying key obstacles, and assessing the overall framework for electric vehicle integration within the country.

2. Research Methodology

This research employs a descriptive and analytical framework that is based on secondary data. Information was gathered from a variety of sources, including government reports, industry publications, academic articles, and official statistics on the adoption of electric vehicles in India. The analysis focuses on data related to trends in electric vehicle sales, infrastructure development, government policies, and market growth. The primary variables investigated include electric vehicle penetration rates, the availability of charging infrastructure, financing challenges, consumer awareness, and the effectiveness of policies. A qualitative methodology was utilized to analyze the data and pinpoint key challenges and opportunities. A comparative analysis was performed to assess India's performance in relation to global trends. Furthermore, insights from the existing literature were integrated to provide a thorough understanding of the factors affecting electric vehicle adoption, and the methodology's reliability and validity were assessed using credible and current sources. Although the study offers valuable insights, it is constrained by its dependence on secondary data.

3. Review of Literature

Digalwar, A. K. et al. (2015) noted that the booming market exerts significant pressure on stagnant resources such as crude oil, natural gas, and fossil fuels. Electric vehicles are regarded as an important option for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Goel, S. et al., 2021). Dixit, S. K. et al. (2022) observed that, despite consumers' positive attitudes toward EVs and substantial policy initiatives by governments worldwide, the adoption of electric vehicles remains challenging. Environmental pollution is currently a global concern (Khurana, A. et al., 2020). Vidhi, R., and Shrivastava, P. (2018) emphasized that increasing the adoption of electric vehicles could help reduce air pollution. Several complex factors influence the widespread adoption of Battery Electric Vehicles in a developing country like India (Chhikara, R. et al., 2021).

The Indian government should allocate more research funding for the development of EVs and charging infrastructure (Singh, V. et al., 2021). Kumar, P. et al. (2020) suggested that policymakers should explore innovative business models and strategies to enhance vehicle utilization and improve the economic viability of EVs. Kore, H. H. et al. (2022) identified significant challenges in developing EV charging infrastructure in India, highlighting the chaotic state of current infrastructure as a major barrier to consumer adoption. Bhattacharyya, S. S. et al. (2021) and Das, P. K. et al. (2022) discussed that electric vehicles are considered viable alternatives to conventional vehicles, capable of overcoming their shortcomings.

Patil, L. N. et al. (2024) state that electric vehicles are gaining popularity on Indian roads; however, challenges such as charging infrastructure and battery life persist. Sachan, S. et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of developing a robust, suitable charging infrastructure to promote the sale and use of electric vehicles in India. Dhar, S. et al. (2017) note that electric vehicles have attracted the attention of Indian policymakers as clean technology alternatives. Kumar, R. et al. (2020) highlight the facilitative role of shared formats in promoting electric vehicle technology. K. V., S., Michael L. K., et al. (2022) suggest that policymakers should revise current policies on electric vehicles in emerging nations. Kumar, A. G. et al. (2015) argue that electric vehicle technology is becoming an integral part of daily life rather than an idealistic concept of the distant future. Biswas, T. K. et al. (1999) recommend that the Indian government develop appropriate policies to accelerate the development and creation of viable electric vehicle markets.

Mittal, G. et al. (2024) highlighted technological advancements and the reliability of electric vehicles, along with India's incentives to promote their rapid adoption. India could thus lead the world toward sustainable development. Saxena, S. et al. (2014) state that India is among the world's fastest-growing economies and ranks as the third-largest vehicle market globally. The annual demand for vehicles in India is increasing rapidly. Digalwar, A. K. et al. (2023) highlight that environmental crises and energy security concerns have driven researchers, environmentalists, and industrialists to pursue cleaner transportation options, with electric vehicles (EVs) emerging as a viable solution for commercial use. Tarei, P. K. et al. (2021) suggest that barriers to EV adoption, including performance and range limitations, total cost of ownership, shortages of charging infrastructure, and lack of consumer awareness about EV technology, are highly influential. Digalwar, A. K. et al. (2021) discuss the potential applications of electric vehicles for original equipment manufacturers and service providers in India.

Das, J. (2022) explains that electric vehicles differ from traditional internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs) and are considered environmentally friendly, with subsidies such as preferential tax rates. Dutt, D. (2023) notes that global EV sales have increased significantly in recent years. Rajagopal (2023) notes that subsidies for EVs in the form of preferential tax rates are a key policy measure. Shalender, K. et al. (2021) state that electric vehicles (EVs), a sustainable form of automobile transportation, can reduce a country's dependence on gasoline while significantly lowering carbon emissions. Nimesh, V. et al. (2020) highlight that the rapid increase in population and urbanization has led to a substantial rise in overall vehicular demand. In India, most vehicles run on conventional fuels, producing harmful gases and particulate matter, which adversely affect human health and the environment.

Jena, R. (2020) noted that the Indian government is taking steps to reduce air pollution by promoting the use of electric vehicles, with success depending on consumers' sentiment, perceptions, and understanding of EVs. Yadav, R. et al. (2024) provide insights for businesses to accelerate the adoption of EVs in the Indian market. Gupta, S. et al. (2023) observe that electric vehicles have become popular because they reduce pollution and promote emission-free transportation. Widespread adoption of EVs may require an effective, efficient charging infrastructure network across the country. Veerendra, A. S. et al. (2022) state that the electrification of the transport sector and the growing popularity of EVs have prompted scientists and researchers to seek charging stations.

Murugan, M., and Marisamynathan, S. (2022) discussed how electric vehicles (EVs) are introduced to mitigate air pollution, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and decrease dependence on fossil fuels. Balasubramanian, N. et al. (2024) examined the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) in emerging economies such as India. Dua, R. et al. (2021) highlighted the Indian government's consideration of deploying plug-in electric vehicles (PEVs) to address air pollution, energy security, and climate change. Dhairiyasamy, R. et al. (2025) suggested expanding the comparative scope to other developing nations and exploring innovative recycling technologies. Singh, S. et al. (2022) indicated that electric vehicles (EVs) have the potential to make a significant contribution to global transportation decarbonization.

Jaiswal, D. et al. (2022) noted that the use of electric vehicles has gained popularity as an alternative fuel option to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and energy costs and is expected to play a crucial role in the future of emerging mobility markets. Shetty, A. et al. (2024) stated that the global automobile industry is striving toward a sustainable future, with emerging countries, including India, preparing for a revolution. Recognizing the importance of customer acceptance for the success of technological shifts, the study aims to identify the catalysts that accelerate the adoption of electric vehicles. Dwivedi, A. et al. (2024) emphasized that electric vehicles are a viable solution to address major global issues, such as rising energy demand and environmental pollution, which is why they are being promoted worldwide.

Praveenkumar, S. et al. (2022) state that India is one of the most populous countries in the world, which has implications for its energy consumption. Higuera-Castillo et al. (2024) provide insights into the factors influencing electric vehicle adoption in different cultural contexts, which can inform policies and strategies to promote sustainable transportation. Attri, R. et al. (2024) encourage the use of electric vehicles, given the increased global focus on green technology. Shankar, A. et al. (2019) highlight that electric vehicles (EVs) are a crucial innovation with the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and help mitigate climate change. Mall, S. et al. (2022) explain that climatic and environmental issues, rapid urbanization, and advancements in renewable energy technologies have contributed to the rise of electric vehicles for sustainable transportation.

Verma, M. et al. (2020) emphasize the role of policymakers in shaping policies to promote and adopt electric vehicles in India. B. et al. (2022) note that increasing environmental concerns necessitate broader implementation of electric vehicles in public fleets. Jerome, S. et al. (2021) consider electric vehicles as an alternative to internal combustion engine vehicles to address concerns over greenhouse gas emissions and dependency on crude oil. Rashmitha, Y. et al. (2024) emphasize the need for a robust network of public charging stations. Modi, Y. (2026) states that India aims to support the clean energy transition and improve air quality by focusing on electric mobility. Rani, P. et al. (2024) call on marketers and policymakers to accelerate the adoption of electric vehicles in emerging markets.

Gayathiri, B. et al. (2025) find that electric vehicles, lower total cost of ownership, technological confidence, environmental consciousness, and government incentives positively influence adoption intentions among potential EV buyers in India. Chaudhary, P. et al. (2023) urge manufacturers and the government to develop and communicate pragmatic value propositions to promote electric vehicles. Jain, V. K. et al. (2025) highlight that electric vehicles improve energy efficiency, reduce air pollution, and support energy independence by decreasing reliance on fossil fuels. Ghatikar, G. et al. (2017) discuss electric vehicle adoption, consumer engagement, and the integration of electric grids within the emerging transportation ecosystem in India.

The integration of electric vehicles has been comprehensively examined concerning environmental sustainability and energy security. Prior studies suggest that electric vehicles (EVs) are essential in decreasing greenhouse gas emissions and alleviating environmental pollution. Research consistently shows that increased EV adoption can significantly improve air quality, particularly in urban areas. Numerous scholars have identified significant obstacles to EV adoption, including high upfront costs, limited driving range, and inadequate charging infrastructure. These issues are especially pronounced in developing nations like India, where economic and infrastructural limitations are more severe. Studies also indicate the significance of consumer awareness and perceptions, implying that misunderstandings about battery life, safety, and performance impede adoption. Policy measures have been recognized as crucial catalysts for greater acceptance of EVs. Government incentives, subsidies, and tax advantages have been demonstrated to positively affect consumer behavior. Moreover, research indicates that innovative business models, such as battery leasing and shared mobility, can improve the economic feasibility of EVs. Charging infrastructure remains a vital element that has been thoroughly explored in the literature. The lack of a robust, accessible charging network creates uncertainty among consumers, reducing their readiness to adopt EVs. Researchers recommend strategic planning and investment in infrastructure development to tackle this challenge. Recent research also underscores the significance of technological progress, especially in battery technology, in improving EV performance and lowering costs. Additionally, growing investments and partnerships between the government and the private sector are expected to accelerate the expansion of the electric vehicle market.

4. Results and Discussion

The analysis reveals a significant increase in the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) in India over recent years. EV sales escalated from approximately 50,000 units in 2016 to over 2.08 million units in 2024. However, despite this growth, EVs accounted for only 7.6% of total vehicle sales in 2024. The adoption of EVs is primarily observed in the two- and three-wheeler segments, which together account for nearly 90% of total EV sales. In contrast, adoption rates for passenger cars, buses, and trucks remain relatively low. The charging infrastructure has experienced rapid growth; nevertheless, it is still insufficient to meet the increasing demand. Forecasts suggest that India will require more than 1.3 million public charging stations by 2030. The existing infrastructure also faces challenges, including low utilization rates, inadequate planning, and a lack of standardization. Financial challenges have been recognized as a major obstacle, particularly for commercial vehicles such as buses and trucks. The high upfront costs and limited access to financing discourage potential buyers.

Additionally, fragmented ownership structures complicate financing options. Consumer awareness and perceptions significantly influence adoption rates. Many consumers voice concerns regarding battery life, driving range, and resale value. The lack of reliable information further intensifies this reluctance. Government initiatives such as FAME I and II, PM E-DRIVE, and production-linked incentives have positively impacted EV adoption. These policies have enhanced domestic manufacturing, reduced costs, and encouraged investment in the EV ecosystem.

The findings reveal that while the uptake of electric vehicles (EVs) in India is increasing, the current pace is insufficient to meet the 2030 target. The dominance of two- and three-wheeled vehicles indicates that affordability and practicality are key factors affecting adoption. However, the slow progress in other vehicle categories highlights the need for targeted interventions. Infrastructure challenges remain a significant barrier. The lack of a well-organized and standardized charging network creates uncertainty for potential buyers. This finding aligns with previous studies that emphasize the critical role of infrastructure in the adoption of EVs. Financial constraints, particularly regarding commercial vehicles, highlight the pressing need for innovative financing solutions. Extending loan terms, implementing priority sector lending, and adopting leasing models could effectively address these financial hurdles. Consumer perceptions play a crucial role in the adoption process. Misconceptions about the performance and reliability of EVs need

to be addressed through awareness campaigns and improved access to information. Government initiatives have effectively promoted EV adoption; however, a shift from incentives to regulatory mandates may be necessary to accelerate growth. Focusing on high-impact sectors such as public transport and freight vehicles could yield significant benefits. The research also identifies opportunities in technological advancements, increasing investments, and favourable consumer attitudes. These factors, combined with strong policy support, could drive the next phase of growth.

5. Conclusion

This study highlighted the growing importance of electric vehicles in India's transition to sustainable transportation. EVs offer significant benefits, including reduced greenhouse gas emissions, improved air quality, and decreased dependence on fossil fuels. Despite notable progress, several barriers hinder widespread adoption. These obstacles encompass high initial costs, inadequate charging infrastructure, financial challenges, and limited consumer awareness. Addressing these issues is essential to achieve India's target of 30% EV penetration by 2030. The study emphasizes the need for a collaborative approach involving government, industry, and research institutions. The development and standardization of charging infrastructure are crucial for building consumer trust. Financial incentives and innovative business models can help ease the economic burden on consumers. Investment in research and development, particularly in battery technology, is vital for improving performance and reducing costs.

Additionally, awareness campaigns should be strengthened to educate consumers about the benefits of EVs. Policy measures should evolve from incentive-based approaches to more structured frameworks, incorporating mandates and targeted actions in high-impact sectors. Initiatives such as achieving 100% EV saturation in select cities can serve as pilot programs for a nationwide rollout. In conclusion, while challenges remain, the potential for EV adoption in India is substantial. With continued efforts and strategic planning, India can position itself as a global leader in electric mobility and achieve a cleaner, more sustainable future.

6. References

- i. Ashok, B., Kannan, C., Usman, K. M., Vignesh, R., Deepak, C., Ramesh, R., ... Kavitha, C. (2022). *Transition to electric mobility in India: Barriers, exploration, and pathways to powertrain shift through an MCDM approach*. *Journal of the Institution of Engineers (India): Series C*, 103(5), 1251–1277. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40032-022-00852-6>
- ii. Attri, R., & Kushwaha, P. S. (2024). *Electric vehicles in India: Identifying the adoption predictors*. *Prabandhan: Indian Journal of Management*, 17(6), 46–62. <https://doi.org/10.17010/pijom/2024/v17i6/173560>
- iii. Balasubramanian, N., Dhalmahapatra, K., Pragma, P., & Sambasivan, M. (2024). *Sustainable transportation in developing countries: Uncovering factors influencing electric vehicle purchase intention in India*. *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 47(7), 1042–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03081060.2024.2313138>
- iv. Bhattacharyya, S. S., & Thakre, S. (2021). *Exploring the factors influencing electric vehicle adoption: An empirical investigation in the emerging economy context of India*. *Foresight*, 23(3), 311–326. <https://doi.org/10.1108/FS-04-2020-0037>
- v. Biswas, T. K., & Biswas, N. M. (1999). *Electric vehicle: A natural option for India? IETE Technical Review*, 16(3–4), 367–373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02564602.1999.11416852>
- vi. Chaturvedi, B. K., Nautiyal, A., Kandpal, T. C., & Yaqoot, M. (2022). *Projected transition to electric vehicles in India and its impact on stakeholders*. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 66, 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2021.12.006>
- vii. Chaudhary, P., & Kate, N. (2023). *The coalescence effect: Understanding the impact of customer value proposition, perceived benefits and climate change sensitivities on electric vehicle adoption in India*. *Business Strategy & Development*, 6(4), 843–858. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.282>
- viii. Chhikara, R., Garg, R., Chhabra, S., Karnatak, U., & Agrawal, G. (2021). *Factors affecting adoption of electric vehicles in India: An exploratory study*. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 100, 103084. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2021.103084>
- ix. Das, J. (2022). *Comparative life cycle GHG emission analysis of conventional and electric vehicles in India*. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(11), 13294–13333. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01990-0>
- x. Das, P. K., & Bhat, M. Y. (2022). *Global electric vehicle adoption: Implementation and policy implications for India*. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(27), 40612–40622. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-18211-w>
- xi. Dhar, S., Pathak, M., & Shukla, P. R. (2017). *Electric vehicles and India's low-carbon passenger transport: A long-term co-benefits assessment*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 146, 139–148.
- xii. Dhairiyasamy, R., & Gabiriel, D. (2025). *Sustainable mobility in India: Advancing domestic production in the electric vehicle sector*. *Discover Sustainability*, 6(1), 52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-025-00844-3>
- xiii. Digalwar, A. K., & Giridhar, G. (2015). *Interpretive structural modeling approach for the development of the electric vehicle market in India*. *Procedia CIRP*, 26, 40–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2014.07.125>
- xiv. Digalwar, A. K., Rastogi, A. (2023). *Assessments of social factors responsible for the adoption of electric vehicles in India: A case study*. *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*, 17(2), 251–264. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJESM-06-2021-0009>
- xv. Digalwar, A. K., Thomas, R. G., & Rastogi, A. (2021). *Evaluation of factors for sustainable manufacturing of electric vehicles in India*. *Procedia CIRP*, 98, 505–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2021.01.142>

- xvi. Dixit, S. K., & Singh, A. K. (2022). *Predicting electric vehicle (EV) buyers in India: A machine learning approach. Review of Socionetwork Strategies*, 16(2), 221–238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12626-022-00109-9>
- xvii. Dua, R., Hardman, S., Bhatt, Y., & Suneja, D. (2021). *Enablers and disablers to plug-in electric vehicle adoption in India. Energy Reports*, 7, 3171–3188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2021.05.025>
- xviii. Dutt, D. (2023). *Exploring multi-level interactions in electric vehicle niche evolution in India. Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 114, 103538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2022.103538>
- xix. Dwivedi, A., Kumar, R., Goel, V., Kumar, A., & Bhattacharyya, S. (2024). *Impact of state-level incentive policy on EV adoption in India. Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 149(22), 12489–12502. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-024-13683-7>
- xx. Gayathiri, B., & Ahamed, S. I. (2025). *Assessing consumer perceptions of electric vehicles in India. Journal of the Institution of Engineers (India): Series A*, 106(1), 155–174. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40030-024-00863-9>
- xxi. Ghatikar, G., Ahuja, A., & Pillai, R. K. (2017). *Battery electric vehicle global adoption practices and distribution grid impacts. Technology and Economics of Smart Grids and Sustainable Energy*, 2(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40866-017-0034-5>
- xxii. Goel, S., Sharma, R., & Rathore, A. K. (2021). *A review of barriers and challenges of electric vehicles in India and vehicle-to-grid optimization. Transportation Engineering*, 4, 100057. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.treng.2021.100057>
- xxiii. Gupta, S., Khanna, R., Kohli, P., Agnihotri, S., Soni, U., & Asjad, M. (2023). *Risk evaluation of electric vehicle charging infrastructure using fuzzy AHP. Operations Management Research*, 16(1), 245–258. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-022-00290-8>
- xxiv. Higuera-Castillo, E., Singh, V., Singh, V., & Liébana-Cabanillas, F. (2024). *Factors affecting the adoption intention of electric vehicles: A cross-cultural study. Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 26(11), 29293–29329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-03865-y>
- xxv. Jain, M., & Singh, A. (2024). *An empirical study on electric vehicle adoption in India: A step towards a greener environment. Transport Policy*, 156, 112–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2024.07.018>
- xxvi. Jain, V. K., Kumari, A., Singh, S., & Tyagi, V. (2025). *Electric vehicles as a pathway to decarbonization in India. Circular Economy and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-025-00619-y>
- xxvii. Jaiswal, D., Kant, R., Singh, P. K., & Yadav, R. (2022). *Investigating the role of electric vehicle knowledge in consumer adoption. Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 29(3), 1027–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-11-2020-0579>
- xxviii. Jena, R. (2020). *Indian consumers' sentiment towards electric vehicles. Industrial Marketing Management*, 90, 605–616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2019.12.012>
- xxix. Jerome, S., & Udayakumar, M. (2021). *Cost-effective electric vehicle charging infrastructure in India. Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 46(12), 12509–12524. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-021-06012-9>
- xxx. Kandpal, R., & Trencher, G. (2025). *Regional disparities in EV policies in India. Energy Research & Social Science*, 125, 104113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104113>
- xxxi. Khurana, A., Kumar, V. V. R., & Sidhpuria, M. (2020). *Adoption of electric vehicles in India. Vision*, 24(1), 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262919875548>
- xxxii. Kore, H. H., & Koul, S. (2022). *Electric vehicle charging infrastructure in India. Management of Environmental Quality*, 33(3), 776–799. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-10-2021-0234>
- xxxiii. Kumar, A. G., Anmol, M., & Akhil, V. S. (2015). *Enhancing EV penetration in India. Procedia Technology*, 21, 552–559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.protcy.2015.10.052>
- xxxiv. Kumar, P., & Chakrabarty, S. (2020). *Total cost of ownership of EVs in India. Transportation Research Record*, 2674(11), 563–572. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198120947089>
- xxxv. Mall, S., & Anbanandam, R. (2022). *Evaluation of EV charging technology in India. Transportation in Developing Economies*, 8(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40890-022-00150-x>
- xxxvi. Mittal, G., Garg, A., & Pareek, K. (2024). *Review of EV technologies and policy implications. Energy Storage*, 6(1), e562. <https://doi.org/10.1002/est2.562>
- xxxvii. Mohanty, P., & Kotak, Y. (2017). *Electric vehicles: Status and roadmap for India.*
- xxxviii. Murugan, M., & Marisamynathan, S. (2022). *Barriers to EV adoption in India. Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 10(2), 795–810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2022.02.007>
- xxxix. Nimesh, V., Sharma, D., Reddy, V. M., & Goswami, A. K. (2020). *Viability of EV transition in India. Energy*, 195, 116976. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.116976>
- xl. Patil, L. N., et al. (2024). *Parameters associated with EV purchase in India. Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 15, 101152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2024.101152>
- xli. Praveenkumar, S., et al. (2022). *PV systems and EV charging optimization in India. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 47(90), 38087–38105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.09.015>
- xlii. Rajagopal, D. (2023). *Energy transition implications for EVs in India. Energy Policy*, 175, 113466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113466>
- xliii. Rani, P., et al. (2024). *Behavioural intention towards EV adoption in India. NMIMS Management Review*, 32(4), 245–256. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09711023241308416>
- xliv. Rashmitha, Y., et al. (2024). *Optimal EV charging station sites in India. Environment, Development and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-024-05746-4>
- xlv. Sahoo, D., Harichandan, S., & Kar, S. K. (2022). *Consumer motives for EV adoption in India. Energy Policy*, 165, 112941. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.112941>

- xlvi. Sachan, S., & Singh, P. P. (2022). *Charging infrastructure planning for EVs in India*. *Regional Sustainability*, 3(4), 335–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsus.2022.11.008>
- xlvii. Saxena, S., Gopal, A., & Phadke, A. (2014). *Electrical consumption of EVs in India*. *Applied Energy*, 115, 582–590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.10.043>
- xlviii. Shalender, K., & Sharma, N. (2021). *TPB model and EV adoption intention*. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 23(1), 665–681. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-00602-7>
- xlix. Shankar, A., & Kumari, P. (2019). *Enablers and inhibitors of EV adoption*. *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing*, 24(4), e1662. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nvsm.1662>
- l. Shetty, A., & Rizwana, M. (2024). *UTAUT2 model and EV adoption in India*. *Management of Environmental Quality*, 35(7), 1505–1523. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-08-2023-0257>
- li. Singh, S., et al. (2022). *EVs for low-emission mobility in India*. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy*, 41(9), 1323–1359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786451.2022.2050232>
- lii. Singh, V., Singh, V., & Vaibhav, S. (2021). *EV trends and policies in India*. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 9(3), 1180–1197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2021.06.006>
- liii. Tarei, P. K., Chand, P., & Gupta, H. (2021). *Barriers to EV adoption in India*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 291, 125847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.125847>
- liv. Veerendra, A. S., et al. (2022). *EV charging infrastructure and policy in India*. *Energy Storage*, 4(6), e335. <https://doi.org/10.1002/est2.335>
- lv. Verma, M., Verma, A., & Khan, M. (2020). *EV adoption in Bengaluru*. *Transportation in Developing Economies*, 6(2), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40890-020-0100-x3>
- lvi. Vidhi, R., & Shrivastava, P. (2018). *EV lifecycle emissions and policy recommendations*. *Energies*, 11(3), 483. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11030483>
- lvii. Yadav, R., & Yadav, R. (2024). *Consumer readiness for EV adoption in India*. *Energy Policy*, 190, 114173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2024.114173>